

ENGLISH AS A MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION: AN EXPLORATION INTO THE PERCEPTION OF TEACHERS IN GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS IN KARAK KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA

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ABSTRACT

While medium-of-Instruction (MOI) has been seen as one of the most crucial decision-making areas in language policies, the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Government has recently decided to shift MOI from Urdu to English. This research aims to know what teachers perceive about the shift in MOI in Government Schools in KP. It also focuses on the impact of the KP government's decision on non-English teachers. This research is quantitative where data is collected through questionnaires and the research has used Grounded Theory. Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss formulated this theory in 1967 because they wanted people to do research deductively to develop new theories. In this type of theory, the researcher does not apply any theory to his work inductively. The study shows that most of the teachers believe that English medium Instruction makes students more brilliant and advanced. It polishes the hidden capabilities of students and makes them more modern.

Keywords: Medium of Instruction, English as a Medium of Instruction, Language Policies.

INTRODUCTION

Language as a source of communication has many purposes. One of them is its use in an academic environment. The language used in the teaching-learning process is called a medium of instruction (MOI) which is not necessarily the native or national language of a country. MOI helps students in developing their cognitive abilities and facilitates their learning. As English is a lingua franca it is widely used as MOI. It enables the learners to compete in the world as it is the language of most of the fields like modern sciences, media, judiciary and research at higher level. So English as a medium of instruction (EMI) is of great importance and prime focus for present-day language planning and policy makers.

MOI has been a controversial issue in Pakistan since it came into being. As Urdu is the native language it was preferred to be the medium of instruction in Pakistan. Later on, private sector schools chose English as MOI creating a distinction between government school students and private school students. English education is often found to be a marker of social divides between privileges and denials (Hamid, M. O., Jahan, I., & Islam, M. M. 2013). As English is becoming a global language so with time provincial governments of Pakistan decided to shift MOI from Urdu to English. The decision of shifting MOI to English was first implemented by the Punjab government in 2009 (Rashid, A., Muzaffar, I., Dar, F., & Butt, S. 2016).

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa government decided to shift MOI systematically at different levels in 2014.

1.1. Problem Statement

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's government's recent change of MOI from Urdu to English has been considered an important decision in regulating uniform curriculum across the province. However the primary stakeholders (teachers) to implement the decision remain uninformed and passive. Keeping in view this state of confusion the current study explores the perception of the teachers about the implementation of English as MOI by KP government and its impact on them.

1.2. Significance

The current study is significant as it explores one of the major causes of disparities resulting from MOI and its impact on our education system. This study recorded the responses of the teachers regarding the decision since they are the practitioners who would turn the policy into public. Then, it serves as an important area of investigation in the field of LPP.

1.3. Research Objectives

The researcher aimed to enable the readers.

- To know how teachers perceive and take KP government's change in MOI from Urdu to English in public sector Schools
- To explore the impact of EMI in public schools in influencing the teaching methodology concerning MOI

1.4. Research Questions

- How do teachers perceive and take KP government's change in MOI from Urdu to English in public sector Schools?
- What is the impact of EMI in public schools in influencing the teaching methodology concerning MOI?

1.5. Delimitation

This study was delimited to Government schools only; it has focused on teachers other than English language instructions. It was delimited to High schools in the district Karak. This research was delimited to Karak because it has a high literacy rate in KPK.

Also, the researcher belongs to that area so it was easy to collect the data.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual Literature

Language policy is a set of principles regarding language behaviour (Hayati et al. 2010). Language planning policy (LPP) is defined as large-scale national planning usually undertaken by governments, meant to influence if not change, the ways of speaking or literacy practices within a society (Baldauf, 2006). In LPP we talk about the language behaviour of a community or country. This policy is mainly related to the language of the education system prescribed by the authorities of a nation (Ager, 2001). LPP shows that teachers are at the receiving end and they are submissive to LPP. The role of the teacher is very passive because the authorities make decisions about language planning and make policies then implement them on the teachers. Teachers are supposed to follow their policy without any objection or intervention. There is no room for their voices in LPP (Zacharias, 2013). LPP in education (LEP) has a top-down role where high authorities take a decision and implement it on others to follow the decision. Medium of Instruction (MOI) is defined as the vehicle for teaching and learning (Hamid et al. 2013). There are two types of medium of instruction in Pakistan Urdu and English. Since Urdu is the national language of Pakistan it was used as MOI in government schools only. On the other hand, English as a medium of instruction (EMI) is a trend in most parts of the world so private sector schools first introduced EMI in Pakistan. In this technological and modern globalised world, everyone needs to compete with the civilised nations of the world so it is only possible through getting a standard education. In the present day, English is considered the standard language so it is believed that EMI provides room for students and teachers to improve their English proficiency.

2.2. Historical Overview of MOI in Pakistan

The emergence of Pakistan in 1947, binding different societies, and talking distinctive languages gave Urdu and English the part of

overwhelming languages. English was the language of the upper class and Urdu was likewise given significance in the recently made nation. Urdu was given exceptional status and in the 1973 constitution it was said that Urdu will be the national language of Pakistan and English will be utilised as an official language just until the point that alternative courses of action are made (Rashid, Muzaffar, Dar, & Butt, 2016). It was likewise pronounced that local languages can be used in educational institutions however to maintain the national solidarity Urdu was chosen as MOI (Rashid et al., 2016). In Gen Zia-ul-Haq's administration, Urdu was announced to be MOI in all schools of the nation and teaching English was made mandatory from Grade four however in 1989 it was made obligatory from Grade 1. A complete shift from Urdu to English was declared in 2009 amid Musharraf's administration while provincial governments were given the choice to choose MOI at the foundation level. The Punjab government actualised the choice of shifting MOI to English from Grade 1 in 2009, in government schools. It was supposed to be actualised in stages (Rashid et al., 2016).

2.3. Previous Studies

The research of Hamid, Jahan and Islam (2013) shows that English helps improve the language proficiency of the students and teachers as well. They are in favour of English as MOI and consider it a complete policy of language in education set by the officials of the government. They discuss MOI policy and practice and investigate how the choices of authorities are actualised on instructors and understudies at the micro level. Their article is based on a contextual analysis which includes educators and students of a private University in Bangladesh. It represents how actors build characters for language through the structure of national MOI policies. It investigates through the interviews that instructors and students develop the foundations of their language in light of their practices and convictions of the language. They propose ramifications of the macro-level MOI arrangements and micro-level practices for learners' content cognition and English

proficiency improvement in a globalising world where English is broadly accepted to hold massive potential for people and social orders as a result of its part in human capital advancement. Hayati and Mashhadi (2010) talk about both the positive and negative influences of political ideology on the language policies of a nation. They explore how political ideologies influence language by using examples of different historical stages and political intervals in the history of Iran, and the different policies adopted in those eras regarding language and language education. Their research suggests that political ideologies affect the use of language and teaching both positively and negatively. They act as an obstacle and a contributor to language use and its teaching. Their research explores the status of the local language and its policies in the modern-day era by looking specifically at foreign language instructing policies after the Islamic revolution and their implications in teaching the teaching-learning process in the educational system of Iran. It also indicates how foreign language teaching is influenced by globalisation, mainly English, by giving several examples from different political eras of Iran.

Bhattacharya (2013) talks about the methodology used in teaching English. Although he is in favour of EMI, he says that if the teaching methodology and the course content are not up to the mark, then it's useless for students to get an education in English medium schools. He led an exploration in an orphanage in rural New Delhi, India, where he observed some multilingual students getting an education in an English-medium town school. He investigates the different education practices that impact the transaction of the medium of instruction, their effect on language learning, and language planning and policy implications. He explored how poor children were getting an education and adopting English in a restricted way by analysing the teaching material, content, course outlines and the teaching methods used. He concluded that those children were not able to access language acquisition because they were not exposed to proper language and content. Many students were enrolled in that

school just because of the school's self-identification as an English medium institute. Still, they were disadvantaged as they were not exposed to the actual system of English medium instruction. Manan, Dumanig, and David (2015) also favour EMI, but their research shows that if the policies are ineffective, students suffer in learning new things to keep up to date. It also shows that the mother tongue should be neglected in teaching-learning because it negatively affects students' acquisition of the new language. Further, it tells us about the classical methodologies and their role in the education system. They conducted research on English teaching crises in Pakistan by collecting data from both teachers and students through questionnaires, interviews and observations. Their research was based on a low-fee private school where most people both teachers and students were of the view that the English teaching policy is not effective and also claimed that teaching the mother tongue is useless and a waste of time. They admitted that the multi-language policy just confuses the students rather than makes them brilliant. They also gave their opinion about the teaching methodologies being used that the grammar translation method is not helpful for students to get an education in a modern way. Their research shows that the respondents did not favour a multi or bilingual education system. Like the above-mentioned research, the study of Alam and Bukhari (2015) also shows that the majority of people want English to be the MOI but not in one step in all grades eventually. It shows that the teachers are not satisfied with the policy of implementing MOI and have objections to the sudden shift of MOI from Urdu to English from the foundation. They conducted a survey at Rawalpindi while collecting data from various schools based on the Punjab Government Education Department's decision to actualise English as MOI. The announcement pronounces that all the books of The Punjab Text book will be in English except Islamic studies and Urdu. Their research shows that this decision should be implemented stepwise because it would be very difficult for students of different

backgrounds to seek education in English. The teachers will also face problems while teaching in English medium so they must be trained properly to solve the issue. The research concluded that the teachers were in favour of the decision but with a systematic implication.

Mohamed (2013) researched the challenges faced by policymakers in making new policies in the education system for the betterment of students' future. He said that in the modern globalised world, the authorities face several challenges as they want to make the students proficient in learning English and balance the emphasis given to the mother tongue of the students. He focused on the influence of MOI on students' intellect, linguistic and cognitive progress. This research especially focuses on an Asian country Maldives where English was adopted as MOI though that has its own particular language and homogenous culture. This case study investigates teachers, students and their parents about the positive effects and challenges for authorities in adopting a second language as MOI while ignoring the mother tongue to be used in the education system of the monolingual and monoculture country. The study shows that the English proficiency of the students is not debatable but the collected data shows that the policy needs to be changed to advance students' learning and cognitive abilities.

Phyak's (2013) research is opposite to all the above-mentioned studies as he considers English as a barrier for the local language to be implemented as MOI. He analysed the challenges a local language faced as MOI in a multilingual country. He conducted the research in a school in Nepal where he investigated the hurdles in the way of implementation and ideology of a local language being used as MOI and the policies implementing the language as MOI. The research shows that such language faces several challenges because other communities resist its implementation as they prefer their language to be used in the education system. The other communities do not allow the policymakers to implement the language of the minority in the education system because of their insignificant social, political and educational status. The article concluded that

English is used as MOI in such areas from very low grades. The survey conducted by Tung, Lam, & Tsang (1997) in Hong Kong where the official or local language is Chinese shows that English is not as practical as MOI, although they prefer English over Chinese generally. The research shows that the parents agree with the teachers about implementing Chinese as MOI because it is adequate to use the local language as MOI.

Tollefson and Tsui (2003) believed that foreign language is harmful to use as MOI, and they mentioned several reasons in their book. They discussed in their book that the medium of instruction is not only related to education and language proficiency, but it also influences other elements like social, political and economic. This is a way of political oppression of minorities, and it

social groups. Further, they mentioned that in a country whose economic condition is not good, only those who will get a good education with the resources there will be high illiteracy, and the poor will be unable to get even the basic needs like health information because everything will be in a foreign language. It also hampers the cognitive abilities and self-perception of those children who struggle to learn the basic expressions of the language. They said that using foreign language in the educational institutes distract children from their culture. Tollefson (2002), in his other book, mentioned that language policies are not only concerned with education it has also link with other aspects of a society e.g. social and political. He mentioned that choosing a medium of instruction is not only a matter of

Year	Researcher(s)	Form of the study	The focus of the study
2013	Hamid, Jahan and Islam	Medium of instruction policy	Their research enables the readers to know that MOI plays a key role in the cognitive development of learners.
2010	Hayati and Mashhadi	Effects of political ideology on language	Their study tells us about the positive and negative effects of political ideology on the language of education.
2013	Bhattacharya	Methodology used in EMI	This survey shows us that the use of improper methodology and content in EMI do not help students to become proficient English Speakers.
2015	Manna , Dumanig and David	Language Policy and Methods of EMI	This research concludes that use of more than one language in education system and grammar translation method disturbs the students' learning ability.
2015	Alam and Bukhari	Language planning and policy	It concludes that MOI should not be changed at once in all grades but rather stepwise.
2013	Mohammed	Challenges faced by policymakers	It is about the hurdles in the way of policymakers while devising MOI e.g. mother tongue.
2013	Phyak	Challenges faced by the local language being MOI	This study is about the problems faced by the local language MOI in a multicultural and multilingual society.
1997	Tung , Lam and Tsang	English as MOI	The result of this survey indicates that local language is effective to be used as a medium of instruction.
2003	Tollefson and Tsui	Medium of instruction policies	The discussion in this book show that foreign language influence social, political and economical elements of a country negatively.
2002	Tollefson	Language policies in education	Language policies are linked with social and political aspects of a society and implementing MOI is a social process.

creates a gap among different ethnic and

language but it is a complete social process.

Table 2.1: List of previous studies.

All of the above-mentioned research studies have been done on different aspects of language planning and policies and English as a medium of instruction, mainly in Western countries. This research is done on the same topic but in a new area with a different perspective. This research aims to fill the gap in the existing knowledge, as no other study has been done on the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa government's decision to

implement EMI. Through this research, the people will know the views and perceptions of teachers of government schools in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa about EMI since it is an important issue. So, many researchers have worked on other aspects, whose list is provided in Table 2.1.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Theoretical Framework

Grounded theory has been applied to this research. Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss formulated this theory in 1967 because they wanted people to do research deductively to develop new theories. This theory suggests that the researcher needs to apply such a method which lets him derive his theory from his work because that is completely applicable and suitable for that particular work. This theory originated as a counterpart of inductive theories where the researcher just applies a theory to his data; in that case he only bounds to that proposed draft. Glaser and Strauss were not satisfied with the existing way of theory application in sociological research. They were of the view that this type of theory is only applicable to special contexts in which they are developed instead of relying on analytical constructs or variables of existing theories. It was a way to provide a space for the emerging of new theories. "We gather data, compare them, remain open to all possible theoretical understandings of the data, and develop tentative interpretations about these data through our codes and nascent categories. Then we go back to the field and gather more data to check and refine our categories (Charmaz and Henwood, 2008: 241)".

3.2. Research Design

This is quantitative research where data was collected quantitatively through questionnaires. The responses of the teachers were collected through likert scale questions. This study has tried to have an insight into the minds of the teachers to know their perception about the implementation of English as a Medium of Instruction (MOI). It gave a direct account of teachers' views and the impact of the decision on them.

3.3. Research Method

This research is exploratory and survey research. This has explored the effect of language planning policy in education. It has

also tried to reveal the views of teachers about the KP government's decision to implement English as MOI. The data was collected in the form of questionnaires so it is also a survey research.

3.4. Sampling

The sample of this research was comprised of thirty-three teachers from three government high schools of district Karak. It preferred the teachers of subjects other than English. It has used a purposive sampling technique to collect the data.

3.5. Procedure and tool

This is a survey research so it has used questionnaires as tools. Questionnaires were comprised of Likert scale questions. Questionnaires were distributed among thirty-three teachers of three government schools of district Karak. To explore their views different types of questions related to their personal experience about MOI were asked. It also aimed to know their experience with teaching in Urdu and the difficulties they are facing because of English as MOI.

4. Data Analysis

The researcher has analysed the data in this section. The critical interpretation of all the questions are given below and the percentage and the detail of the views of the teachers about each question are provided with pie charts.

Knowledge about national language

Most of the teachers strongly agreed with this question as Urdu is our national language so twenty-six teachers know it very well. Five of the teachers simply agreed to the statement which shows that they can communicate in this language and two are neutral which indicates that they only understand but do not have command over the language. None of the teachers from the selected sample has shown a negative response to this question.

Pie chart 4.1.

Knowledge about any other language than Urdu in Pakistan

This question was about familiarity with any other official language i.e English in our country. The result shows that eleven teachers strongly agreed, nine just agreed which means that they can understand and

communicate in English. Nine of them are neutral to this question which shows they are just familiar with the language but cannot communicate two disagreed and one strongly disagreed which means they do not know the language at all.

Pie Chart 4.2.

Superiority of Urdu

As we know English is considered to be superior to any other language because it is the most widely used language but the teachers responded very differently as they consider Urdu to be superior. The number of teachers who strongly agreed and agreed to this question are twenty three so they

believed that Urdu is superior to English. It may be because of their affiliation with this language. Furthermore, seven teachers were neutral, maybe they consider both languages the same and four teachers disagreed that Urdu is superior so they might consider English superior to Urdu.

Pie Chart 4.3.

Importance of learning Urdu language for a bright future

For a responsible citizen, it is very important to value his own culture and language. So it

is necessary to sustain our own identity in this globalised world by knowing our language. Urdu is important to be learned as our national language for our true

representation twenty-two teachers agreed, seven were neutral and four disagreed with this statement which shows their inclination

towards Urdu. The percentage of the responses is given below.

Pie chart 4.4.

Learning Urdu is easier than English.

Everyone has his own opinion that either Urdu is easy or English so twenty-one teachers out of thirty-three believe that Urdu is easy to learn four consider both the

languages same in learning may be easy or difficult and nine consider Urdu learning difficult as they disagreed with the above statement.

Pie Chart 4.5.

Both Urdu and English are important to learn.

Multilingualism is considered to be very important in modern day. It is said that a multilingual person has very sharp mentality than monolingual. The opinion of the teachers about multilingualism was asked so

twenty eight teachers has shown positive response which shows that they believe that it is very much important to know more than one language, two remained neutral and three did not consider it important to learn both English and Urdu.

Pie chart 4.6.

Views about the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa government's decision to shift MOI

In this world of competition, everybody wants their children to get an education in an

advanced environment. Most of the private sector educational institutes preferred English as MOI and KP government also shifted MOI to English recently in public

sector educational institutes. The reaction of the teachers from the selected sample shows that twenty-six teachers are happy with the decision as they think that it is a good step taken by the KP government, two are neutral

and five do not favour the decision at all. Five teachers are not in favour of the decision which suggests that maybe they are unable to teach in EMI.

Pie Chart 4.7.

English is easy if taught at the Primary level. Everything is difficult when we encounter it for the first time whether is learning a language or doing some other practice. So, most non-native learners think that English is difficult to learn because it requires a lot of effort and time to learn a new language.

However the result of this question illustrates that twenty-four teachers out of thirty-three believed that English is easy to learn if taught from the foundation level, four have shown neutral reactions and five do not consider it easy.

Pie Chart 4.8.

Teaching in English Medium In teaching learning process the part of the teacher is very crucial and the method and language which he/she uses in the class is

also of great importance. However the result demonstrates that twenty six teachers agreed and can easily teach in English, five neutral and two disagreed to the statement.

Pie Chart 4.9.

EMI: An Impact on the Academic Standard EMI has advantages as well as disadvantages as twenty nine teachers feel that EMI creates

a difference between modern students and those who were taught in Urdu medium, two did not show any kind of positive or negative

response towards the statement and two disagreed.

Pie Chart 4.10.

Shift of MOI to English at a higher level

Some people believe that it is advantageous for students to study in English medium at a higher level not at primary level because at that time the children are more vulnerable to their native language so it is not easy to accommodate the foreign language. A similar

view was given by twenty-one teachers as they strongly agreed and agreed to the above statement and five did not show any positive or negative approach towards this question and remained neutral. Seven teachers were not in favour of teaching English at a higher level.

Pie Chart 4.11.

The issues of the students when they get promoted to English medium at a higher level

Children can learn any language easily as compared to adults because with the development of their cognitive development their language skills become as natural as

their mother tongue. Since they are exposed to a new language from the beginning then they will not suffer any linguistic problems at a higher level when they are promoted to the English medium. Twenty-seven teachers in the survey were in favour of this view, four were neutral and two disagreed.

Pie Chart 4.12.

Learn by understanding the concepts.

Some students get the concept easily by studying in their native language but those who have command over another language

can understand that well. In the survey, twenty-two respondents favoured that EMI helps students to know everything clearly,

nine were non-judgmental and two did not favour the statement.

Pie Chart 4.13.

English language skills provide more opportunities for students and professionals. In this globalised world where the English language is of more importance, most people believe that those who have good English skills can have more opportunities in any

field as compared to those who lack those skills. So a similar view was presented by twenty-seven teachers in response to the above statement, four were non-reactive and two disaccorded.

Pie Chart 4.14.

The English language is a fashion more than a talent in modern society.

Generally, talent is associated with how efficient a person is in communication skills but nowadays the idea of fashion has been incorporated into the concept of language skills, especially the English language. Those

who can speak English fluently are considered modern and they too use that language as a fashion. Twenty teachers supported this notion that English is a fashion, not a talent, four respondents were neutral to this idea and nine rejected it.

Pie Chart 4.15.

English language skills lead to a brilliant future.

As English is a lingua franca it is necessary to have strong command over it. If you can communicate with people and express yourself at any forum then you will be able to have a good status or career in society

because you will know how to make ways to make a good future more than those who do not know English. The result of the survey reveals that eighteen teachers thought the same, eight did not have any opinion and seven did not accept this.

Pie Chart 4.16.

Knowing English is a sign of a highly qualified and well-educated person.

In this modern world, we use English as a marker of high qualification and consider those people highly qualified who know it. The approach of nineteen teachers was positive which suggests that they also

consider English as a sign of high qualification. Six teachers were viewless and eight refused to accept this view because they do not take the English language as a measure of high qualification and intelligence.

Pie Chart 4.17.

Good English language skills can help students and graduates have good jobs.

As we relate English language skills with a good job most of us think that those who are masters in language skills can get jobs easily. When there are job interviews then those

people who have command over the English language are given importance. This survey suggests that nineteen teachers responded positively, eight were non-responsive and six did not intend that this argument is right.

Pie Chart 4.18.

KP government's decision to shift MOI

The teachers were asked if they favour the KP government's decision of implementing EMI so twenty-seven teachers supported this which indicates that they are happy with the decision of taking this step by the

government. Furthermore, they think that it can advance our learning and helps students to represent themselves better in this age of competition. The response of four teachers was neutral and a single teacher disfavoured the step.

Pie Chart 4.19.

Linguistic issues in our education system

Majority of us think that EMI strengthen our communication skills which ultimately solve the problems associated with the language.

Twenty five of thirty three teachers think that it helps us to overcome our linguistic issues in academia, four did not show any opinion and four were against the statement.

Pie Chart 4.20.

UMI: Sense of Identity Crisis

Twenty-one teachers considered that in this age of competition where everyone is getting education in English medium those who are still in Urdu medium will feel worried about their career because they will not be very

confident about their performance on any platform. Five did not think that either the shift of MOI would affect those students or not and seven thought that I would not influence them.

Pie Chart 4.21.

EMI will make students more brilliant

Twenty-four teachers appreciate this step of the government as they are of the view that it will make the students more intelligent

because English is believed to be an advanced language which makes students competent, Ideas were pointless and six discouraged this idea.

Pie Chart 4.22.

EMI discourages Urdu medium students

It is believed generally that students get discouraged by seeing others getting an education in English medium. However,

twenty-one teachers believe the same. And five did not show any reaction and seven disagreed.

Pie Chart 4.23.

EMI encourage Students to feel proud

As English is considered superior to any other language that is why students enrolled in English medium schools feel that they are superior to other students. They think that they are getting into a more advanced

environment. So they feel proud. Anyhow, the views of twenty-two teachers were in favour of this argument, seven did not show any regard and four showed negative responses as they disagreed.

Pie Chart 4.24.

EMI's role in improving the learning skills of students

A student can learn in a friendly and understandable environment. When they feel comfortable in any medium whether it is Urdu or English, it enhances their learning

skills because learning is more related to their interest. The result indicates that Twenty four teachers showed agreed that EMI will play a key role in improving learning skills of students, four were opinion less and five did not approve the notion.

Pie Chart 4.25.

English medium is a sign of advancement.
 As we know that English is the language of advance people so majority of the students when enrolled in English medium

institutions reckoned themselves more modern. Same view was presented by twenty three teachers while two remain neutral and four were disagree.

Pie Chart 4.26.

EMI motivates students to learn with more passion
 The students who are interested more in academic actives, they are more enthusiastic and put more effort into learning to achieve their goal of learning with more passion. Leaning in their native language makes them

passive and effortless by having acknowledgement of the language already. So twenty-seven teachers agreed to the view that EMI encourage students to learn with more passion, two remained pointless and four showed disagreement with the particular statement.

Pie Chart 4.27.

Embarrassment while communicating in English
 Speaking and understanding English language is a prestige in our society and when the teachers were asked about personal experience of embarrassment of

understanding English in front of others then twenty three teachers admitted that they feel embarrassment in front of others, two did not consider this idea and six made it clear by disagreeing that they never feel embarrassment in this regard.

Pie Chart 4.28.

Communication in English

Majority of us perceived that if you have full grab over a language then you can present yourself in a finer manner similarly if the students know English likewise they know Urdu then it will be easier for them to

communicate in it. Twenty teachers are agreed as they thought English is as easy as Urdu while communicating in, six did not intend to answer whether it is positive or negative and seven disregarded the statement.

Pie Chart 4.29.

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Table 4.1

Question no.	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly disagree	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1	26	78.78%	5	15.15%	2	6.06%	0	0%	0	0%
2	11	33.33%	9	27.27%	11	33.33%	2	6.06%	0	0%
3	12	36.36%	11	33.33%	7	21.21%	4	12.12%	0	0%
4	12	36.36%	10	30.30%	7	21.21%	4	12.12%	0	0%
5	9	27.27%	12	36.36%	4	12.12%	8	24.24%	0	0%
6	20	60.60%	8	24.24%	2	6.06%	1	3.03%	2	6.06%
7	14	42.42%	12	36.36%	2	6.06%	2	6.06%	3	9.09%
8	18	54.54%	6	18.18%	4	12.12%	5	15.15%	0	0%
9	12	36.36%	14	42.42%	5	15.15%	2	6.06%	0	0%
10	11	33.33%	18	54.54%	2	6.06%	2	6.06%	0	0%
11	12	36.36%	9	27.27%	5	15.15%	7	21.21%	0	0%
12	9	27.27%	18	54.54%	4	12.12%	2	6.06%	0	0%
13	6	18.18%	16	48.48%	9	27.27%	2	6.06%	0	0%
14	15	45.45%	12	36.36%	4	12.12%	2	6.06%	0	0%
15	13	39.39%	7	21.21%	4	12.12%	8	24.24%	1	3.03%
16	8	24.24%	10	30.30%	8	24.24%	7	21.21%	0	0%
17	9	27.27%	10	30.30%	6	18.18%	8	24.24%	0	0%
18	5	15.15%	14	42.42%	8	24.24%	6	18.18%	0	0%
19	15	45.45%	13	39.39%	4	12.12%	1	3.03%	0	0%
20	12	36.36%	13	39.39%	4	12.12%	4	12.12%	0	0%
21	9	27.27%	12	36.36%	5	15.15%	5	15.15%	2	6.06%
22	14	42.42%	10	30.30%	3	9.09%	4	12.12%	2	6.06%
23	7	21.21%	14	42.42%	5	15.15%	4	12.12%	3	9.09%
24	6	18.18%	16	48.48%	7	21.21%	4	12.12%	0	0%
25	9	27.27%	15	45.45%	4	12.12%	5	15.15%	0	0%
26	8	24.24%	15	45.45%	3	9.09%	7	21.21%	0	0%
27	8	24.24%	19	57.57%	2	6.06%	4	12.12%	0	0%
28	9	27.27%	14	42.42%	2	6.06%	6	18.18%	2	6.06%
29	5	15.15%	15	45.45%	6	18.18%	7	21.21%	0	0%
30	16	48.48%	11	33.33%	3	9.09%	3	9.09%	0	0%

EMI will help to learn modern sciences well
 Modern sciences are the discovery of English people. When you study in original form rather than translated form then it enables you to learn the concepts more clearly. A

translated work lacks its originality so the result shows that twenty-seven teachers appreciated learning in EMI, three remained neutral and three did not think that EMI improves our learning skills.

Pie Chart 4.30.

The current study "English as a Medium of Instruction: An Exploration into the Perception of Teachers in Government Schools in Karak Khyber Pakhtunkhwa" deals

with knowing the views of the teachers about EMI. For this purpose, the researcher has conducted a survey and distributed questionnaires among thirty-three teachers

comprised of thirty questions about the national language which is Urdu, English and both as MOI. In this regard, the overall percentages of the various questions are given in Table 4.1. Seventy-eighty (78%) percent is the highest value in this table which shows that most of the teachers know the national language very well. The second highest number is sixty (60%) percent which shows that most of the teachers believe that both Urdu and English are important to learn. The overall percentages indicate that the majority of the teachers are in favour of EMI because they believe that English is a modern language so it makes our students brilliant. They believe that it is prestigious in modern society to know the English language and students also feel proud by being in English medium schools. They also believe that it creates a gap between those students who have studied at UMI. The survey also reveals that the teachers appreciate the decision of the Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to implement EMI in all grades. It polishes the hidden capabilities of the students and provides the teachers with a chance to teach in the most advanced language. It also helps the students in the development of their cognitive system and makes it sharper. It enables the students of Government schools to compete with those children who were studying in EMI at private schools from the very beginning.

Conclusion

In this section the researcher has discussed the findings of this study. The current study "English as Medium of Instruction: An Exploration into the Perception of Teachers in Government Schools in Karak Khyber Pakhtunkhwa" has used Grounded Theory to analyse the views of the teachers about EMI. The researcher has aimed to answer the research questions and the study includes knowing the perception of non-English teachers regarding the shift in the medium of instruction from Urdu to English and exploring the impact of this decision on teachers. The researcher has used quantitative methods to collect and analyse the data to achieve the above-mentioned goals.

The researcher selected a sample of teachers from three Government schools in Karak Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to explore their perception of EMI. The sample included the teachers of all the subjects except English because they can best tell whether English is good to be a medium of instruction or whether it is difficult for them to teach in English. They believe that EMI provides students an opportunity to learn in an advanced environment so they can also learn modern sciences. It also enables them to communicate easily and present themselves in a good manner at every forum. The responses also show that they believe that Urdu is also important to be learned because it is our national language. However, English and Urdu both are given equal importance but English is the demand of modern society so it should be focused on more. Thus the questionnaires were distributed among thirty-three teachers through a purposive sampling technique in three different Schools in Karak. The teachers were of different ages and qualifications so thirty different questions were asked about EMI.

The data is presented in the form of pie charts with critical description and the researcher has calculated it in numbers and percentages. The findings show that most of the teachers are in favour of EMI. It shows that they appreciate the decision of Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa of implementing EMI.

Recommendations

This section highlights the possible avenues and research areas to be explored in further studies. Language planning and policies is an important field of research which could be further explored in an academic context through the perspective of the perception of Students. Moreover, it could be researched through a comparative manner between the teachers and students.

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